

IRISH TRADITIONAL ETHNOMUSICOLOGY ANALYSIS USING DECISION TREES AND HIGH LEVEL SYMBOLIC FEATURES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we investigate the suitability of decision tree classifiers to assist the task of massive computational ethnomusicology analysis. In our experiments we have employed a dataset of 10,200 traditional Irish tunes. In order to extract features from the Irish tunes, we have converted them into MIDI files and then extracted high level features from them. In our experiments with the traditional Irish tunes, we have verified that decision tree classifiers might be used for this task.

1. INTRODUCTION

Within the Music Information Retrieval (MIR) community there is a consensus that MIR-based methods and tools might be used to assist musicologists with the task of analyzing large music collections [1–6]. This general problem is known as Computational Ethnomusicology, but it was only in the last few years that this problem started receiving more attention by the MIR researchers. In [5] the authors clarify that the term musicology is normally used by music scholars to refer to the study of European and European-derived art music traditions and for this reason the term ethnomusicology is normally used to refer to the study of art music traditions in other cultures. However, when dealing with Computational Ethnomusicology, the term ethnomusicology should be considered as the study of all the world's music [5].

There are several approaches that can be used to aid Computational Ethnomusicology [7–9]. However one important issue that should not be overlooked, when developing or using existing MIR technology to assist with Computational Ethnomusicology, is the comprehensibility of the results provided by the approach. In other data mining application domains, such as Medicine and Finance the issue of comprehensibility is high valued [10]. That is because the users of the system need to understand the reasoning of the algorithm for making that decision / suggestion. Although there are several ways that knowledge can be represented and used with different algorithms, the use of Rules

is the most common one as it is easily interpretable even by non-expert users. This is one of the reasons why some of the recent research in Computational Ethnomusicology has used association rule mining algorithms [11–13]. The association rule mining algorithms generate a list of rules about facts that often happen together in a dataset. This type of algorithm allows the user to have a series of specific rules that might contain novel knowledge for the musicologist, but they do not allow the user to have a global feeling for the data.

The main contribution of this work is to explore the suitability of a decision tree classifier [14] to assist the task of Computational Ethnomusicology. Note that contrary to the association rule mining algorithms used in prior Computational Ethnomusicology research, the decision tree classifier provides additional benefits beyond just creating a rule-based representation. The first advantage is that the user can explore the tree visually. The second advantage is that the tree representation provides information about the interaction between the attributes and their values used to make the decisions. If a musicologist can understand the reasoning behind the attributes, then they can further ask for other types of information to also be made available in the data or suggest novel attributes because of the confusion being made by the classifier. However, for this to be possible, it is necessary to use high level symbolic features. For this reason in this work we employ the jSymbolic framework [15] that provides us with several high level symbolic features that can be extracted from a MIDI file.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a brief introduction to some of the ethnomusicology aspects of the Irish Traditional Music. Section 3 presents the experimental settings used in this work. Section 4 presents the computational experiments. Section 5 presents the conclusions and future research directions.

2. IRISH TRADITIONAL MUSIC

In this section we briefly explain some of the interesting points of the Traditional Irish Music Ethnomusicology. One definition used in this work is that as long as a tune is part of the Irish repertoire of Irish Traditional musicians, then it is considered to be part of Irish Traditional Music, regardless of the fact that it may have originated in other cultures. Therefore the Traditional Irish Musician reper-

toire also assumes that other folk songs and tunes, such as Polish and English songs, can also be considered as being part of Irish tradition. Furthermore, is remarkable how much these tunes change according to the region where the tunes are played and this can make them look like totally different tunes [16].

2.1 ABC Notation

The ABC notation is a music notation format that is expressed in plain text format. It was designed primarily for folk and traditional music of Western Europe origin (such as Traditional Irish music). It's history walks beside the growth of the Internet, where the ABC notation has become very popular. There are now lots of tunes in ABC format, from a variety of online collections. There are also several music notation software tools that are able to read the ABC notation, convert it to the standard music notation format or play it directly to the the speakers of a computer.

One of the most important aims of the ABC notation is that it can also be easily read by humans, as opposed to other computer-based music notations. Therefore, with a little practice, it is possible to play a tune directly from the ABC notation. Figure 1 presents a tune in ABC notation. Figure 2 presents a short excerpt of the same tune in standard music notation.

Cooley's REEL

```
X: 1
T: Cooley's
R: reel
M: 4/4
L: 1/8
K: E Dor
|:D2|EBBA B2 EB|B2 AB dBAG|FDAD BDAD|FDAD dAFD|
EBBA B2 EB|B2 AB defg|afec dBAF|DEFD E2:|
|:gf|eB B2 efge|eB B2 gedB|A2 FA DAFA|A2 FA defg|
eB B2 eBgb|eB B2 defg|afec dBAF|DEFD E2:|
```

Figure 1. Example of ABC Notation

Figure 2. Cooley's (Reel)

2.2 The Session Website

The Session website (<http://thesession.org/>) is a non-profit endeavor as an online community dedicated to Irish traditional music. It was created in 1999, and up to this day it is maintained by its collaborators. The website contains over 13,000 Irish tunes in the ABC notation with embedded plug-ins which allow users to download the MIDI File or the Music Sheet of a given tune.

2.3 Irish Music Genres

2.3.1 Reel

One of the oldest Irish dances, reels are performed in 4/4 time. They are believed to have been played in Ireland for the first time in the late 1700s. The reel is performed either solo or in a group, in several contexts, like competitions, exhibitions or socially [17]. One of the characteristics of the reel are two groups of four notes each, adding up to an eighth-note bar. Within each group there are two heavy-light pairs [16]. Figure 2 presents a short excerpt from one of the most popular reel tunes according the thesession.org website.

2.3.2 Barndance

A traditional genre generally performed to 4/4 rhythm, but, related to marching practice, danced to 6/8 time in North County Antrim. The barndances were most popular as social dance up to the 1950s. Its name comes from the practice of dancing in 'barns' (large sheds) which was common prior to the provision of social and meeting halls, and this assigns to this genre a rural association [17]. Figure 3 presents a short excerpt from the most popular barndance tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 3. The Star of the Country Down (Barndance)

2.3.3 Hornpipe

Performed in 4/4 time with a characteristic dotted rhythm and with accents occurring on beats one and three. Historically, the hornpipe comes to Ireland via England, at the end of the eighteenth century, performed by professional dancers between acts in plays, and has maritime associations. This heritage gave a exhibitionistic face to Irish hornpipes [17]. It should be noted that not all hornpipes are notated with dotted rhythms and are usually played with swing even though the sheet music is not dotted. Figure 4 presents a short excerpt from the most popular hornpipe tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 4. The Rights Of Man (Hornpipe)

2.3.4 Jig

These tunes are noted in 6/8 time, generally performed in competitive and exhibition dance contexts, choreographed by both males and females. The characteristic pattern of the jig is two groups of three quavers. These tunes are structured in two eight-bar sections, each section repeated twice (AABB) [17]. Figure 5 presents a short excerpt from

the most popular jig tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 5. The Kesh (Jig)

2.3.5 Mazurka

A dance-form in 3/4 time which within the context of Irish musicians, was popularized to the greatest extent in Donegal, where it arrived in the first half of the nineteenth century. However, mazurka emerged in the Polish province of Mazovia, in the 1500s [17]. It is distinguished from its cousin waltz [16] by its unique emphasis on the second, rather than the more expected first, of the three beats. While the rhythm of the Donegal mazurkas conforms completely to the definitive Polish pattern, the phrasing structure of these correspond to that used in other Irish rhythms, and shows no connection with the mazurkas of eastern Europe [17]. Figure 6 presents a short excerpt from the most popular mazurka tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 6. Sonny's (Mazurka)

2.3.6 Polka

A popular dance form notated in 2/4 time, popularly performed with march-like rhythms. It was developed in Bohemia in the early eighteenth century and arrived in Ireland in the late 1800s. It is most commonly associated with the counties of Cork, Kerry and Limerick, but polkas have spread them throughout Ireland [17]. Figure 7 presents a short excerpt from the most popular polka tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 7. Ryan's (Polka)

2.3.7 Slide

A tune type associated with the jig, slides are performed faster and in 12/8 time. The predominant rhythm involves the alternation of crotchets and quavers creating the feeling of long and short. Slides are essentially dance music and the long-short rhythm of the tune is echoed by the movements of the dancers [17]. Figure 8 presents a short excerpt from the most popular slide tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 8. The Road To Lisdoonvarna (Slide)

2.3.8 Slip Jig

This different type of jig is performed in 9/8 time, generally used for group dances. Unlike the other jig types, musically the slip jig is in single form; its two-part, eight-bar music structure is not repeated. Its characteristic rhythmic pattern is three groups of three quavers. It is often referred to as “the queen of step dances” to indicate the required gracefulness of the dance [17]. Figure 9 presents a short excerpt from the most popular slip jig tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 9. The Butterfly (Slip Jig)

2.3.9 Strathspey

These tunes, notated in 4/4 time, originated in Scotland in the middle of the eighteenth century. They arrived in Ireland in the late nineteenth century, in Donegal, although it never functioned for the dance there. The strathspey is in common time with each beat of a bar being accented. The tune type is particularly noted for its dotted rhythms, especially the “Scots snap”, where the short note precedes the long note [17]. Figure 10 presents a short excerpt from a popular strathspey tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 10. Calum's Road (Strathspey)

2.3.10 Three-two

Three-twos are a different march-like form performed in 3/2 time and may have origins in the the application of triple meter to the hornpipe form [18]. Figure 11 presents a short excerpt from the most popular three-two tune according the thesession.org website.

Figure 11. An Drochaid Chliuteach (Three-Two)

2.3.11 Waltz

The waltz is a dance-form in 3/4 time, particularly distinctive for the strong accent given to the first beat in each bar. Its origins are uncertain, but it may date from the fourteenth century, unrelated to the European minuet. The tunes are generally sung or played on fiddle, and have agricultural associations [17]. Figure 12 presents a short excerpt from the most popular waltz tune according to the thesession.org website.

Figure 12. Si Bheag Si Mhor (Waltz)

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS

3.1 Database Construction

In order to perform our experiments we have created a novel Irish Traditional Music dataset. In order to create the dataset we have automatically retrieved all the tunes available from thesession.org website. However, the website only had the tunes in the ABC format, and in order to extract symbolic features from the tunes we needed to convert this data to the MIDI format. Therefore, the creation of the dataset was composed of three main stages: (1) ABC download; (2) ABC to MIDI conversion; (3) MIDI (Symbolic) Feature Extraction. Table 1 shows the final result of this process.

3.1.1 ABC Download

In order to automatically retrieve all the tunes from thesession.org website we developed an algorithm that uses the PHP function cURL in a loop. The cURL function returns a string with the retrieve HTML webpage for a given URL. For each tune webpage we have used a set of regular expressions to find and extract the ABC notation within a given webpage. After the extraction of the tune in ABC format we place it in a specific folder according to the Traditional Irish genre. With this procedure we managed to retrieve 11,980 tunes in the ABC format.

3.1.2 ABC to MIDI Conversion

As mentioned earlier in order to extract symbolic features to create the dataset, we need the tunes to be in the MIDI format. Therefore, in order to convert the downloaded ABC tunes to the MIDI format we have employed an online converter. Note that the number of successfully converted ABC to MIDI tunes was 10,200 MIDI files.

3.1.3 MIDI (Symbolic) Feature Extraction

After the tunes have been converted into the MIDI format, we have used the jSymbolic¹ software [15] to extract high level symbolic features from the MIDI files. This is particularly important, as high level symbolic features can be

¹ Available at: <http://jmir.sourceforge.net/jSymbolic.html>

interpreted by musicologists. With the jSymbolic software we extracted a total of 1,022 high-level symbolic features that fall into the broad categories of texture, rhythm, dynamics, pitch statistics, melody and instrumentation.

Tune type	Number of tunes	Relative Number
barndances	298	2,92%
hornpipes	843	8,26%
jigs	2,666	26,14%
mazurkas	116	1,14%
polkas	695	6,81%
reels	3,864	37,88%
slides	228	2,24%
slip jigs	380	3,73%
strathspey	329	3,32%
three-twos	78	0,76%
waltz	703	6,89%

Table 1. Number of Irish Traditional Tunes

Tune type	Precision	Number of leaves
barndance	26,1%	55
hornpipe	84,7%	38
jig	100%	1
mazurka	49,5%	9
polka	100%	1
reel	94,2%	35
slide	100%	1
slip jig	100%	1
strathspey	60%	39
three-two	100%	1
waltz	91,3%	15

Table 2. Precision by genre

4. RESULTS

In this section we are interested in answering the following questions by using controlled experiments: How well can a Decision Tree Classifier predict the genre labels of the 11 Irish music genres? Can the generated decision tree be used as a tool to assist Computational Ethnomusicology?

4.1 Irish Music Genre Classification

In order to perform the experiments reported in this section we have used the J48 Decision tree classifier implementation of the WEKA data mining toolkit [19]. The experiments were performed using stratified ten-fold cross-validation.

The experimental results of the classification experiment are presented in Table 2. The analysis of the results presented in Table 2 shows that overall, the precision across all Traditional Irish genres was high (92,3%). This result means that 9,418 tunes were correctly classified. However, It should be noted that in some particular Irish Traditional genres, like barndance, the obtained results are much lower

a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	classified as
64	51	0	0	0	160	0	0	23	0	0	a = barndance
38	739	0	0	0	9	0	0	57	0	0	b = hornpipe
0	0	2666	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	c = jig
0	0	0	54	0	0	0	0	0	0	62	d = mazurka
0	0	0	0	695	0	0	0	0	0	0	e = polka
118	20	0	0	0	3684	0	0	42	0	0	f = reel
0	0	0	0	0	0	228	0	0	0	0	g = slide
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	380	0	0	0	h = slip jig
25	63	0	0	0	58	0	0	183	0	0	i = strathspey
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	78	0	j = three two
0	0	0	55	0	0	0	0	0	0	647	k = waltz

Table 3. Confusion Matrix

Figure 13. General vision of the decision tree.

Figure 14. Three first levels of the generated tree.

Figure 15. Deepest path of the generated decision tree

than this overall result. In order to understand the confusions being made by the decision tree classifier, let us analyse the confusion matrix presented in Table 3.

The analysis of the confusion matrix presented in Table 3 shows that the low precision for the tunes of the barndances Irish Traditional genre corresponds to the same misconception made by naive listeners due the musical similarity of the genres. In the case of the barndances, the genre that had the lowest precision, the tunes were mostly classified as reels. This misclassification might be due to the fact that both genres has the same Initial Time Signature, i.e. 4/4. The same type of error happens with mazurkas, that are usually confused with its cousin, the waltz [16].

4.2 Analysis of the Generated Tree

One of the advantages of using a decision tree classifier is that it allows us to visually inspect the generated tree and that it also outputs the classification rules. The decision tree algorithm used in this work had as the input a feature vector of 1,022 features (described in [20]) for each tune. The final generated decision tree employed 105 attributes (out of the 1,022) to create a decision tree with 393 rules

and 197 leaves. Figure 13 presents a general vision of the tree, where the letters represents the genres at the leaves.

The first levels of the generated tree are presented in detail in Figure 14. The analysis of just these first three levels of the tree shows some interesting insights. First, it shows what an individual who is not trained in Irish Traditional music perceives while listening to the different Irish Traditional Tunes. A naive listener may perceive that a given tune is in a 3/2 time signature (although not necessarily naming it is a 3/2 time signature). However this naive listener will have trouble pin-pointing whether this song is a waltz or a mazurka. That is of course, only if this listener knows Mazurkas exist, otherwise the listener will classify it as a Waltz.

Second, one important aspect of a decision tree is that it visually shows the importance of each and how they were used (i.e. with which values and/or decision splits) to make a decision. By using decision trees in combination with high level symbolic features, this information can aid musicologists to validate the automated approaches and/or look closely at the data to verify if a mistake was really made. It might even be possible for musicologists to

request the creation of new high level symbolic features from the Music Information Retrieval research community based on their knowledge if they verify that there is important information missing. Due to space limitations it is not possible to plot in detail the complete generated decision tree, however in Figure 15 we present the deepest path of the generated decision tree in detail. The analysis of Figure 15 shows that the distinction between two of Irish music genres involves several different aspects of the tunes.

Third, in this experiments we have only looked at one aspect of interest by musicologists, i.e. the classification of genres (and more importantly what are the different properties that distinguishes them). We argue that this same approach (using high level symbolic features with a decision tree classifier) might be used to assist with other musicological tasks such as auto tagging and music discovery, among others.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have showed that a decision tree classifier might be used as a Computation Ethnomusicology tool to assist musicologists. In order to perform our experiments, we have created a novel dataset with 10,200 Irish Traditional Tunes obtained from the www.thessesion.org website. The tunes are available on the website using the ABC notation and therefore we converted all the tunes into MIDI files. We then used the jSymbolic feature extractor to obtain high level symbolic features from the MIDI files. With the high level symbolic features extracted from the MIDI files, we have trained a decision tree classifier, which correctly classified 9,418 tunes.

After the classification, the decision tree classifier has the advantage of producing a graphical model (a decision tree) and also a set of rules. By analyzing the decision tree, it became clear that on the first three levels of the tree, the high level symbolic features of Compound or Simple Meter, Triple Meter and Initial Time Signature were shown to correspond to the perception made by a naive listeners, i.e. the distinction between the different Irish Traditional genres, starts by using the rhythm information. This particular result shows that decision trees might be used to aid musicologists.

As future research we plan to perform experiments with other rule-generating methods on different datasets and to use the methodology proposed in this paper to other computational ethnomusicology tasks.

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